

Annunciating Teachers' Continuous Professional Development

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ABSTRACT

Teacher training develop educational skills that are compatible with the education policies and to enable teachers to deliver these policies. The aim of this study is has shown the importance of continuous professional development of elementary teachers as perceived by them gained in the implementation of the questionnaire. The study offers recommendations for learners and providers of professional development opportunities. Schools must have a responsibility to encourage and nurture their own love of learning, and educational organizations have the responsibility to create conditions and provide tools and procedures for helping teachers experience learning situations.

KEYWORDS: *Professional Development, Descriptive Methods of Research, Educators*

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INTRODUCTION

To ensure the highest standards of professional practice and promote thereby the public interest in safeguarding life, health and property, the Commission through Resolution No. 2008-466 series of 2008 provides for a continuing professional education program for all regulated professions. This Resolution shall be known as the Continuing Professional Development Program Guidelines or the CPD Guidelines, which stipulates, "The state recognizes the role of professionals in nation- building and provides for the sustained development of a reservoir of professionals under Section 14, Article XII of the Constitution". In a press release, the CPD law was enacted to upgrade the practice of Filipino professionals in line with the integration of economies of the member countries of Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN), as required by the ASEAN Mutual Recognition Arrangements, the Philippine Qualifications Framework, and the ASEAN Qualifications Reference Framework. It mandates all professionals to take additional formal and non-formal training through CPD for the renewal of their Professional Identification Card every three years, effective July 1, 2017. In order to address this issue, Republic Act No. 10912 of Sec. 15. states that "the PRC and the PRBs, in consultation with the AIPO/APO and other stakeholders, shall promulgate the implementing rules and regulations (IRR) within six (6) months from the effectivity of this Act. However, a PRB may prescribe its own requirements or procedure relating to the CPD as may be pertinent and applicable to the specific profession: Provided, that the same does not contravene any of the provisions of this' Act and its IRR. The researcher understood the essence

and importance of academic studies in the field of teaching. Thus, this research deepened the understanding of teachers to their vital role in the teaching-learning process and how it will affect their perception to life. Such understanding is about the teachers as the center of transforming their knowledge into the learners to the best of their abilities in a simplest manner that is easily understood by them.

Theoretical Background

This study is anchored on the theories and legal basis as illustrated in figure 1. The bases of this study are the theories of Leslie Watkins, Graf Christian von Ehrenfels and Jean Piaget. According to Wikipedia Life-long Learning (Colloquialism) is the "ongoing, voluntary, and self-motivated" pursuit of knowledge for either personal or professional reasons. In addition, two theories of particular relevance when considering lifelong learning are cognitivism and constructivism. Cognitivism, most notably Gestalt theory, speaks of learning as making sense of the relationship between what is old and what is new. Similarly, Constructivist theory states that "knowledge is not passively received from the world or from authoritative sources but constructed by individuals or groups making sense of their experiential worlds". Constructivism lends itself well to Lifelong learning as it brings together learning from many different sources including life experiences. The term "Gestalt," comes from a German word that roughly means pattern or form. The main tenet of the Gestalt theory is that the whole is greater than the sum of its parts; learning is more than just invoking mechanical responses from learners.

As with other learning theories, the Gestalt theory has laws of organization by which it must function. These organizational laws already exist in the make-up of the human mind and how perceptions are structured. Gestalt theorists propose that the experiences and perceptions of learners have a significant impact on the way that they learn. He added in his theory of values that “desiring a thing means either desiring the existence of a thing, or possession of it, in which case the desire is directed at an existence, though not of the thing itself, but rather of its availability, and at the same time at a non-existence, the absence of all disturbances which obstruct that availability”. (Ehrenfels 1897, 53)

Piaget's (1936) theory of cognitive development explains how a child constructs a mental model of the world. He disagreed with the idea that intelligence was a fixed trait, and regarded cognitive development as a process which occurs due to biological maturation and interaction with the environment.

The goal of the theory is to explain the mechanisms and processes by which the infant, and then the child, develops into an individual who can reason and think using hypotheses.

To Piaget, cognitive development was a progressive reorganization of mental processes as a result of biological maturation and environmental experience. Children construct an understanding of the world around them, then experience discrepancies between what they already know and what they discover in their environment.

Results and Discussion

The profile of the different respondents is the advisers of the different grade levels and specializations. The profiles of the teachers are determined in terms of age and gender, highest educational attainment, number of years as a teacher, number of years as teacher in current post, grade level, area of specialization, trainings and seminars attended and position.

Table 1 Age and Gender Profile of Teachers
n=21

Age Range	Male	Percentage (%)	Female	Percentage (%)	Total No. Teachers	Total Percentage
56-60			2	11.11	2	11.11%
51-55	1	5.56	4	22.22	5	27.78%
46-50			3	16.67	3	16.67%
41-45	1	5.56	4	22.22	5	27.78%
36-40	1	5.56			1	5.56%
31-35						
26-30						
20-25	1	5.56	1	5.56	2	11.11%
Total	4	22.24	14	77.78	18	100%

As shown in the table, female teachers that age ranges from 51-55years old and 41-45 years old tied at the frequency of 4 which is 22.22 percent of the total respondents closely followed by the ranges 46-50 years old female teachers with the frequency of 3 and is 16.67 percent. Next is the frequency of 2 which is 11.11 percent female teachers and age ranges 56-60. Lastly is the frequency of 1 which is 5.56 percent female teachers and age ranges 20-25. Obviously, a range of 51-55 years old and 41-45 female teachers got the total frequency of 4 and 1 respectively which is 22.22 percent for females and 5.56 percent for males. Evidently, it shows that the total female teachers are 8 or 44.44 percent that outrank the male of 1 or 5.56 percent. Age and gender profile are variables that affect the perception of teachers towards continual growth and development they have in their respective station. This implies that average age of 51-55 for both male and female teachers are efficient enough to give and describe their perception towards their continuous professional development.

Objective of the Study

This research seeks to determine the teachers’ growth and development at Matalom North Central School, Matalom, Leyte as basis for continuous plan. It will includes the profile of the respondents and level of teaching performance to fully understand their nature with regards to growth and development.

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive survey method using a purposive sampling. The scheme included the inputs from the data gathered from the respondents of the elementary teachers in MatalomNorth Central School of Matalom. The Municipality of Matalom, is a 3rd class municipality in the province of Leyte, Philippines. According to the 2015 census, it has a population of 33,121 people. It was said that the Spaniards once saw the flaming red of the fire treesthat dotted the shores of Matalom Beach and the scenic Canigao Island and asked the natives the local dialect for "hermosa" or beautiful. The natives answered "Matahum" or "Matalom." This was the origin of the town's name. Matalom North District is one of the district of Matalom. It is composed of twelve (12) elementary schools situated in the different barangays of Matalom municipality.

The input of the study contains the indicators on their continual growth and development of teachers as to security, monetary, working conditions, social, job status, achievement/responsibility, and recognition. The process contains the transmittal letter, answered questionnaire and the teacher’s performance rating of teachers. Computation on data gathered is based on the chosen statistical treatment.

Educational Attainment

The level or highest education achieved by the teachers also affects their performance towards the manifestation of continual growth and development. Table 3 presents the educational attainment of the teachers as subordinates.

Table 2 Highest Educational Attainment of Teachers
n=21

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Master's Degree plus 30 credits	3	16.67
Master's Degree plus 15 credits	1	5.56
Master's Degree	2	11.11
Bachelor's Degree plus 42 credits	1	5.56
Bachelor's Degree plus 24 credits	9	50.00
Bachelor's Degree plus 15 credits	1	5.56
Bachelor's Degree	1	5.56
Total	18	100.00

As reflected in the table, teachers who earned Bachelor's Degree plus 24 units in education got the highest percentage of 50.00% that outnumbered the Master's Degree plus 15 units, Bachelor's Degree plus 42 credits and Bachelor's Degree graduates only of 5.56 percent with a frequency of 1. This means that teachers are not quiet competent enough as classroom managers and are not striving to become more competent in professional aspect as shown in the percentage of finishing their masteral degree as well as in becoming the next school head if ever.

Position

The positions of teachers affect their work competence and data are presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Position of Teachers
n=18

Position	Frequency	Percentage
Master Teacher 2	1	5.56
Master Teacher 1	2	11.11
Teacher 3	11	61.11
Teacher 2	2	11.11
Teacher 1	2	11.11
Total	18	100.00

As shown in table 4, Teacher 3 position got the highest of 61.11 percent which is 11 out of the total respondents of 18. Master Teacher 1 and Teacher 2 and Teacher 1 got 11.11 percent which is 6 of the total teachers. The least in number is master teacher 2 which is only 1 out of 18 teacher respondents. This implies that the teachers need more requirements to meet for a higher position in order to increase salary grade as well as appointed into higher position like principal or head teacher.

Number of Years in the Service

The years in service is another factor considered for the competency of teachers I the workplace. Table 4 presents the length of service that the teacher respondents served in the teaching position.

Table 4 Teaching Experience
n=18

Length of Service	Frequency	Percentage
26 or more	3	16.67
21-25	3	16.67
16-20	4	22.22
11-15	6	33.33
1-5	2	11.11
Total	18	100.00

As presented it was found out that 11/15 years of experience shows a highest percentage of 33.33 which have a frequency of 6 closely followed by 16-20 years' experience which is 4 and is 22.22 percent. Noticeably 26 or more years and 21-25 years got the second in rank of 16.67% and the least is 1-5 years of experience. Length of service accounts for the degree of the perception rated to their school heads in terms of governance and continual growth. This also means that the higher in years in the position, the more mature enough in the profession.

Grade Level/SpecializationTable 5 Grade Level
n=18

Grade Level	TOTAL	Percentage
6	3	16.67
5	3	16.67
4	3	16.67
3	3	16.67
2	2	11.11
1	3	16.67
Preschool	1	5.56
TOTAL	18	100.00

As shown in the table that the grade level 6, 5, 4, 3, and 1 got the highest number of teachers with 16.67 percent. This implies that the school has the greater number of teachers prior to its location.

Relevant Trainings/Seminars Attended

Trainings are part of professional development and enhancement of teachers' profession. Table 6 presents the relevant trainings participated by the teacher respondents as subordinates to their school heads.

Table 6 Relevant Trainings and Seminars Attended/Participated
n=18

Nature of Relevant Trainings	Frequency	Percentage
National		
Regional	16	88.89
Local	2	11.11
TOTAL	18	100

The table shows that out of 71 responses from 48 respondents, local trainings which are handled in the district or school level got the highest nature of trainings attended by the teachers that ranks one followed by the regional trainings with – responses and the least is the national level trainings account for only – responses. This implies that the teachers need enough training in the national level and if possible in the international conferences in order to increase professional development as part of the criteria for teacher performance. Trainings and seminars attended account also on the behavior a teacher as part of their continual growth and development.

The summary of all the ratings of the respondents with regards to the perception of all ratings of the respondents to the perception of different domain indicators were presented in Table 7 in which means scores can be compared to the others as to the highest and lowest in terms of the domains shown.

Table 7 Summary of Mean Values Score for Domain Indicators as Rated by Different Respondents

Domain 1	4.25	Exemplary
Domain 2	4.31	Exemplary
Domain 3	4.12	Advanced Proficiency
Domain 4	4.22	Exemplary
AVERAGE TOTAL MEAN	4.23	Exemplary
Standard Deviation	0.07	

Table 7 presents the mean values score on the perception of continual growth and development by the different group of respondents (Exemplary) showed high degree level of perception for continuous professional development.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

In the course of the study, the following findings were gathered from the analysis of the data. The profile of the different respondents varies in which the elementary teachers attain the minimum and needed profile under Civil Service Qualification for Professional Teachers. Perceived domain indicators rating of the of the different respondents showed high degree level of perception for continuous professional development with a mean rating of 98.75 describe as 75.25 followed by 221.25. In terms of perceived performance level of teachers, the group of respondents rated an overall grand mean of high for instruction. Finally, the result showed no significant mean differences exist in the statistical computation of classroom strategies and behavior,

and significant mean difference occurred as to the variables for planning and preparation, reflecting on teaching and collegiality and professionalism.

CONCLUSION

In the result of the study presented, it is concluded that to achieve high and competitive school performance requires continual growth and development that enhances teacher's capabilities. Demonstrated positive practices lead to greater impact to different stakeholders. Teachers have the potential to influence student achievement through their effectiveness and efficiency through decision making. To teach is to do all these and more, influence every child entrusted in our care

to become better and happier so that life becomes more meaningful.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following are recommended:

1. A proposed training plan for sustainability and maintenance of the continuous professional development by the teachers in order to gain strong capacity of acquiring best practices in the workplace.
2. Trainings are not only intended to few selected individuals but everyone also thus, it is recommended to have a rotation of teachers by grade level so that everybody may have equal opportunity to be trained. Embed opportunities for professional learning and collaborating with colleagues.
3. Invest in teacher learning by allocating at least 10percent of the budget to professional development. To be provided concrete, professional development to enhance their current skills and teach them new skills.
4. Involve teachers in the study of their content and methodology. Provide teachers with skills that will allow them to determine that student learning is improving.

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